

A kinetic study of photochemical oxidation of sucrose by chloramine-T in acidic medium

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Abstract : The kinetics investigation of oxidation of sucrose by chloramine-T in acidic medium has been carried out in presence of visible light. The reaction has a first order dependence on chloramine-T. With excess concentration of other reactants the reaction rate follows a fractional order kinetics with respect to substrate. The reaction is catalysed by H⁺ ions as well. A small salt effect and increase in reaction rate with increasing the intensity of light source is also observed. Addition of *p*-toluene sulphonamide retards the reaction rate. The various thermodynamic parameters have been calculated from the rate measurements at different temperatures.

Keywords : Kinetics, photochemical oxidation, sucrose, chloramine-T.

Introduction

Carbohydrates are the essential biomolecules and a chief source of energy for living system¹. The oxidation of carbohydrates and fats in living system is a free radical reaction and we get energy from these exothermic reactions². Thus the oxidation of carbohydrates is a basic source of life. There are several reports available in the literature on the oxidation of carbohydrates and other compounds by different reagents³⁻²¹ but the photochemical oxidation with chloramine-T as an oxidant has not been investigated. Chloramine-T (*p*-Me-C₆H₄SO₂N-ClNa) abbreviated as CAT is a versatile oxidizing agent. Therefore we have chosen CAT to study the oxidation of some carbohydrates in presence of visible light. In the present paper, we report the kinetics of photochemical oxidation of sucrose.

Results and discussion

Reaction order with respect to chloramine-T :

In a typical kinetic run, a plot of log (*a*-*x*) versus time gave a straight line which indicates that the reaction under the chosen conditions follows pseudo-first order kinetics. The order with respect to oxidant is unity (Table 1).

Table 1

Sl. no.	[Sucrose] = 5.0 × 10 ⁻³ M, [HCl] = 1.0 × 10 ⁻³ M [CAT] × 10 ³ M	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹ (Average)	<i>k</i> × 10 ⁴ s ⁻¹ (Graphical)
1.	3.7	2.33	2.36
2.	5.0	2.54	2.40
3.	6.2	2.90	3.00
4.	7.5	3.32	3.40
5.	8.8	3.89	3.86
6.	10.0	4.59	4.45

The results reveal that the value of rate constant increases as the concentration of CAT increases. It is because the increase in [CAT] generates more HOCl which acts as an oxidizing species.

Reaction order with respect to substrate :

On varying the concentration of sucrose from 1.2 × 10⁻³ to 7.5 × 10⁻³ an increase in reaction rate was observed. The plot of log *k* versus [substrate] gave a straight line with a slope suggesting that the order with respect to substrate is fractional (Table 2).

Reaction order with respect to acid :

On varying the hydrochloric acid concentration from

Table 2

[CAT] = $10.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [HCl] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Sl. no.	[Sucrose] $\times 10^3$ M	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ (Average)	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ (Graphical)
1.	1.2	3.08	3.09
2.	2.5	3.39	3.17
3.	3.7	3.88	3.56
4.	5.0	4.59	4.45
5.	6.2	4.94	4.76
6.	7.5	5.15	5.25

Table 3

[CAT] = $10.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Sucrose] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Sl. no.	[HCl] $\times 10^3$ M	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ (Average)	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ (Graphical)
1.	0.2	2.64	2.51
2.	0.4	2.97	2.91
3.	0.6	3.26	3.29
4.	0.8	3.75	3.59
5.	1.0	4.59	4.45

1×10^{-3} to 5.0×10^{-3} an increase in reaction rate was observed. The plot of $\log k$ versus $[H^+]$ gave a straight line suggesting the reaction order with respect to acid is unity (Table 3).

The cause of increase of reaction rate with increasing acid concentration may be explained due to following reaction²²⁻²⁴ :

Thus an increase in acid concentration results in the formation of more HOCl, consequently the reaction rate increases.

Effect of variation of Cl^- ion concentration :

The role of chloride ion in the kinetics of the oxidation reaction by CAT is very crucial. The plot of $\log k$ versus $[Cl^-]$ gives a straight line showing an increase in reaction rate with increase in Cl^- ion concentration. The cause of acceleration in reaction rate is the generation of HOCl due to the interaction between a chloride ion and a chloronium ion produced by the hydrolysis of N-Cl bond (Table 4).

Table 4

[CAT] = $10 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Sucrose] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$,
[HCl] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Sl. no.	[KCl] $\times 10^3 M$	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ (Average)	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ (Graphical)
1.	0.4	3.68	4.10
2.	0.6	4.15	4.22
3.	0.8	4.57	4.35
4.	1.0	5.04	5.13

The cause of enhancement in reaction rate is due to the generation of HOCl according to the following reaction²⁴ :

Therefore the increase in concentration of chloride ion produces more of the HOCl which is the active oxidising species of reaction and thus an increase in the reaction rate is observed.

Effect of variation of intensity of light :

The reaction rate increases with the increase in the intensity of light source. The graph of rate constant versus light intensity indicates the enhancement of reaction rate with the increase in intensity of light source. This is because on increasing the intensity, the number of photons striking per unit area increases (Table 5).

Table 5

[CAT] = $10.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Sucrose] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$,
[HCl] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Sl. no.	Light intensity (W)	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ (Average)	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ (Graphical)
1.	40	3.17	3.09
2.	60	3.48	3.13
3.	100	3.89	4.08
4.	200	4.59	4.45

Effect of variation of temperature :

The reaction has been studied by varying the temperature of reaction system and an increase in reaction rate has been observed with increase in temperature (Table 6). Further a plot of \log of rate constant versus reciprocal of temperature is also linear in both the cases which proves the validity of Arrhenius equation.

Table 6

[CAT] = $10.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Sucrose] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$,
[HCl] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Sl. no.	Temp. (K)	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ (Average)	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ (Graphical)
1.	303	3.33	3.03
2.	308	3.48	3.34
3.	313	3.77	3.60
4.	318	4.15	4.22
5.	323	4.70	4.84

Effect of addition of p-toluene sulphonamide :

The addition of PTS, one of the reaction product, from 1.0×10^{-3} to 4.0×10^{-3} at constant CAT and substrate concentration, decreases the reaction rate.

This decrease is the result of mass-law effect according to which the addition of product causes the reversal of reaction and hence the reaction proceeds in backward direction²⁵. This further supports the fact that HOCl is the oxidizing species (Table 7).

Table 7

[CAT] = $10.0 \times 10^{-3} M$, [Sucrose] = $5.0 \times 10^{-3} M$,
[HCl] = $1.0 \times 10^{-3} M$

Sl. no.	[PTS] $\times 10^{-3} M$	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ (Average)	$k \times 10^4 s^{-1}$ (Graphical)
1.	0.4	3.05	3.26
2.	0.6	2.92	3.03
3.	0.8	2.77	2.81
4.	1.0	2.51	2.38

Kinetics and activation parameters :

The values of enthalpy of activation, entropy of activation and free energy of activation give an idea about the progress of reaction. It has been observed that if ΔH^* is positive, ΔS^* is negative and ΔG^* is positive then the reaction is non spontaneous²⁶. This fact has been confirmed by carrying out the reaction in dark and at room temperature (i.e. without heating) and no reaction was observed in that condition which shows that the reaction needs some initiation which can be provided by means of light or heat (Table 8).

Mechanism :

On the basis of experimental findings and results a tentative mechanism has been proposed for the photo-

Table 8

Sl. no.	Activation parameter	Sucrose
1.	Energy of activation (E_a)	14.340 kJ mol ⁻¹
2.	Frequenc factor (log PZ)	2.96
3.	Enthalpy of activation (ΔH^*)	11.70 kJ mol ⁻¹
4.	Entropy of activation (ΔS^*)	-192.2 JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹
5.	Free energy of activation (ΔG^*)	70.89 kJ mol ⁻¹

chemical oxidation of sucrose by chloramine-T.

In acidic medium, there occurs first the hydrolysis of disaccharide i.e. sucrose into monosaccharide units and then the further reaction of oxidation takes place.

The mechanism for the dissociation of CAT giving HOCl has already been given. The HOCl dissociates photochemically into free radicals as follows :

These OH[•] radicals bring about the oxidation of carbohydrates. The Cl[•] radicals combine with the H[•] radicals produced during oxidation to give HCl which has been detected by bringing the rod dipped in NH₄OH on the flask. The evolution of CO₂ has been confirmed by lime water test. The overall reaction for the oxidation is :

The stepwise reaction mechanism given in Scheme 1.

Experimental

Materials : The chemicals used were of analaR grade and doubly distilled water was used throughout to prepare the solutions. The required volumes of sucrose, CAT, HCl and other reagents, where necessary, were mixed in a 250 ml beaker. The reaction vessel was kept under visible light source (tungsten lamp, $\lambda = 5780-5920 \text{ \AA}$).

Kinetics : The course of the reaction was followed by withdrawing 2 ml of reaction mixture at a definite time interval and adding it to a flask containing potassium iodide solution to quench the reaction. The unreacted chloramine-T quickly reacts with KI solution and liberates iodine which was titrated against standard sodium thiosulphate solution as titrant using starch as indicator.

Analysis of reaction products : Sucrose (9 g/100 ml), CAT (0.563 g/100 ml) and water were mixed in a flask

Scheme 1

and the flask was kept under tungsten lamp. After completion of the reaction (as indicated by TLC), the light source was removed. The spots obtained on the TLC plate were found to be of formaldehyde and formic acid by co-TLC with the authentic samples. The products were further confirmed by qualitative tests. The development of reddish brown colour with Nessler's reagent changing to yellow green confirms formaldehyde as one of the reaction product. The development of red colour with ferric

chloride solution and also the evolution of carbon monoxide with conc. H_2SO_4 , which was confirmed by flame test, indicates the formation of formic acid as another product.

Conclusion :

The kinetics of photochemical oxidation of sucrose by CAT in visible light can be concluded as follows :

- (i) The reaction order with respect to oxidant is one.
- (ii) The order with respect to acid is one.

(iii) The reaction shows fractional order dependence with respect to substrate.

(iv) Due to photochemical condition the reaction follows radical mechanism.

(v) The reaction rate shows an acceleration with increase in the intensity of light source.

(vi) The values of enthalpy of activation, entropy of activation and free energy of activation give an idea about the progress of reaction. It has been observed that ΔH^* is positive, ΔS^* is negative and ΔG^* is positive then the reaction is non spontaneous. The above fact has been confirmed by placing the reaction system in dark at room temperature where no reaction occurred which indicates that the reaction needs some initiation either by heat or light.

(vii) The photochemical oxidation of sucrose by chloramine-T in acidic medium gives formic acid, formaldehyde, CO_2 , water and HCl as the reaction products.

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